

Research on the primary school teachers' preparation for the implementation of competence-based approach (CBA) in Djibouti

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to investigate the role that has been played by the teachers' level of training, their perception of the CBA curriculum, and institutional preparedness in the successful implementation of CBA. The study carries out a survey on primary school teachers in Djibouti. The survey targeted primary school teachers in Djibouti aged above 22 years. A sample of 300 teachers participated in this study. Through quantitative approaches, study establishes that the current level of teacher training in primary schools contributes to the effective implementation of the CBA approach in Djibouti. It was also established that perceptions of primary school teachers towards the CBA approach influence their willingness to implement it in Djibouti, and that institutional preparedness influences the accommodation and implementation of the CBA approach in Djibouti. The analysis has further demonstrated that teacher training accounts for 54.6% of the effective implementation of the CBA approach, while perceptions of primary school teachers towards the CBA approach accounts for 64.5%. Most importantly, institutional preparedness explains 49.5% of the effective implementation of the CBA approach. Djibouti has been in the process of implementing the competency-based curriculum to move away from the teacher-centered, exam-oriented approach, and this study sought to determine factors that affect successful implementation. This study is first of its kind in Djibouti.

Keywords: CBA, new approach, teacher preparedness, teacher training, teacher perception, Competency-Based Assessment for learning

Introduction

The country of Djibouti is a multi-ethnic nation with a population of approximately 1.1 million (World Bank, 2023), and its official languages are French and Arabic. Like other nations in Africa and across the globe, Djibouti also recognised the need to align its education system with the changing demands of the 21st century. As per World Bank (2019), the evolving economy necessitates more than mere school attendance. Students must attain essential skills in core subjects such as algebra, vocabulary, and science to thrive in both personal and professional spheres. Additionally, they should develop effective communication skills, problem-solving abilities, and teamwork expertise. This aligns with the novel Competency-Based Approach (CBA), which emphasizes a practical orientation for learners. Hernandez and Menendez (2017) and Akinrinola (2020) highlighted the deficiency in labor skills among individuals undergoing the Competency-Based Education (CBE). They further emphasized that this deficiency is reflective of the experiences encountered in schools or universities worldwide. Proficiencies such as effective communication, critical thinking, and the ability to engage in lifelong learning are the competencies that are fostered through this educational approach (Alainati, 2021; Tembei & Len, 2024).

The primary purpose of Competency-Based Approach (CBA) is to assess a learner's ability after completing a curriculum. It is adaptable across the institutions of diverse scales, offering a solution to global changes in personnel knowledge supply and demand through collaborative efforts. According to Rw'abarezi (2018), the adoption of the Competency-Based approach (CBA) in Rwanda has progressed significantly, with the majority of teachers being trained in CBA. However, a primary challenge lies in teachers resisting change and clinging to the familiar knowledge-based curriculum. Teachers perceive the new curriculum as more demanding and complex. The Competency-Based Approach underscores continuous assessment methods over exams-based approaches, aiming to identify, develop, and manage learners' capabilities and skills.

The education system of Djibouti is a 5-4-3 system; this means that elementary or primary school takes five years to complete, middle school or lower secondary takes four years and high school or upper secondary takes three years. Students begin school at the age of six. Improving Djibouti's education system tops the development policies of its government. In 2000, its government began reforming the education system that, focused on improving the quality of schooling and expanding its access. In 2010, the government made public another plan, one that would focus on improving its education system (Seife, 2020). Some of the aims that were included in the plan were to achieve 100% enrolment in primary schools by 2019, achieve gender equality by 2019 and improve pre-school education while collaborating with local institutions, communities and the private sector (Kate Luft, 2017).

In 2016, approximately 64.3% of the students managed to complete primary school, and approximately 44% of the students managed to complete lower secondary school in Djibouti (Kate Luft, 2017). Despite the country working towards the promotion of gender equality in the education system, a wide gap still exists between female and male enrolment (Tzannatos, 2024). For instance, more females were out of school than males in 2016. In the previous year, 46% of the females were out of school, and 39.3% were the males that were out of school. In addition, 68.6% were male students that enrolled in primary schools in 2016, and 60.9% were female students who managed to enrol (Kate Luft, 2017).

In Djibouti, pre-primary education consists of two years, and this is the first stage of basic education. Primary school consists of five grades and typically begins at the age of five/six (Scholaro database, 2023). The primary education curriculum includes subjects such as, among others, Islamic education, physical education, social studies, Science, Mathematics, French, Music, Arts and Arabic (RocApply, 2022), with French being the primary language of instruction. According to Kate Luft (2017), in 2007, the primary gross enrolment rate of Djibouti, that is, the percentage of children that had been enrolled in primary school, was 50%. In 2014, statistics increased to 68%, with the author documenting a significant drop in 2016, 64.8%. A 2023 article by the Oxford Business Group reported that in 2021, the number of students that were being enrolled on primary schools in Djibouti had increased to 73%.

Building on various recommendations and consensus, the government of Djibouti came up with a Ten-Year Perspective Plan (Schéma Directeur 2000–2010). In 2000, the government passed a new law in the field (d'orientation du système éducatif) and prepared and launched the Medium-Term Plan 2000-2005 (Plan d'action à moyen terme). This initiative was aimed at improving the quality of instructions, increasing the role of communities and parents, introducing the competence-based approach (CBA) and strengthening the capacity of non-formal and private systems so as to reach the youths that had not enrolled in school, and especially girls (Moussa Idriss et al, 2018).

Often referred to as competency-based education (CBE), the CBA is an educational framework whose focus is on the mastery and development of particular skills or competencies rather than simply completing the curriculum or spending time in a classroom (rather than simply completing a set curriculum or accumulating time in a classroom) (Chauvigné & Coulet, 2010; Tahar, 2023). According to the researchers, the approach is also highly valuable for teachers. For Djibouti, the CBA has promoted an integration of scholastic objectives and a closer relevance to Djiboutian realities into the development of the nation.

The past decade(s) has seen the CBA enter primary schools in Djibouti, but not without generating new stakes or sparking debates between the opposers and supporters of the approach. According to Chauvigné & Coulet (2010) and Tahar (2023), this approach was also developed for teachers, especially for the development of new teaching practices, for instance, around professionalism. Research on the approach

shows that the level of preparedness among teachers and the learning institutions in general for the implementation of the CBA is a critical challenge in Africa, therefore warranting significant consideration (Sifuna & Obonyo, 2018; Nombo, 2022). Djibouti is no exception, as articles by the World Bank, UNICEF and UNESCO highlight similar challenges. As Djibouti embarks on educational reforms and especially CBA implementation, there appear concerns about the readiness of primary school teachers and the institutions in general. Additionally, the lack of studies on the topic in the country is significantly contributing to the lack of knowledge on the approach.

Teachers are likely to require guidance and support to adapt to the CBA in a manner that respects and incorporates local traditions and values. Therefore, to ensure the absolute success of the approach, primary school teachers need to be adequately prepared to embrace and integrate the principles of the approach into their teaching practice.

Review of Related Literature and Theory

Theory

The theory that underpins this study is the constructivism learning theory. As a learning theory, Sadker & Sadker (2005) argued that constructivism promotes individual learning. This highlights the importance of a teacher letting a learner create meaning from the issue or topic being discussed. Gordon (2008) and Makewa (2019) stated that constructivism is a philosophy that basically advocates the need for learners to be considered and treated as human beings and not mere machines that await information feeding. It, therefore, becomes clear that students are not put to school as blank slates that ought to be written on but are individuals that possess the ability to construct knowledge. Kim (2005) contrasted constructivism teaching with conventional teaching, claiming that traditionally, learning has been assumed to be repetitive, a basic process involving the imitation of newly offered knowledge in tests. On the other hand, constructivism aids learners in the internalization and transformation of new information and ideas.

The constructivist learning theory advocates for learners to receive chances to talk and work in groups, learn via observations, and play with others (Stanley & Stanley, 2007; Lombardi, 2021). Therefore, any activities carried out outside or inside the classroom ought to prepare learners to become active players in real life and the society. This also means that teachers ought to be equipped with the necessary skills and possess the necessary values that can facilitate the creation of a warm learning environment. Researchers such as Zheng & Borg (2014) and Tahar (2023) stated that teachers are required to follow certain guidelines provided by curriculum developers, which suit the CBA. For the CBA to be successful, Botha & Reddy (2011) shared similar thoughts as Zheng & Borg. According to Botha & Reddy, teachers are critical in ensuring the success of the CBA; as a result, they ought to be knowledgeable enough to involve student involvement in the learning process. Similarly, Moodley (2013) and Christoforidou and Kyriakides (2021) stated that teachers need to have expertise in specific subjects so that they yield targeted products.

Therefore, the current study applies this theory to show the essence of equipping teachers with Pedagogical Content Knowledge that will allow the learners to learn through knowledge developed by their teachers. The theory also emphasizes the role of both the student and the teacher in implementing CBA. It can, therefore, be concluded that for the CBA to be successfully implemented in Djibouti, the roles of the teachers ought to be clearly defined and that the teachers ought to possess relevant pedagogical knowledge; at the same time, students should be willing to participate in the learning and teaching processes.

Role of Teacher Training in effective implementation of the CBA approach

According to Duc et al. (2017) and García et al. (2022), professional competency for teachers is a significant task of the education sector and institutions training teachers, and this is because this is the premise at which teachers receive quality information. It is also a premise that fosters the creation of quality teaching staff that are released to meet the ongoing and presumably long-term demands of any education system. Duc et al. (2017) and García et al. (2022) claim that it is during this process that teachers develop professional

competency for students before beginning their careers. Therefore, the researchers argue that before implementing the CBA, it is important that teachers receive training as this is a matter of content and concern that necessitates the need to be updated.

Generally, according to a UNESCO report, there exists a lack of in-service and initial training for teachers and general school staff members in Djibouti despite the introduction of the Education Sector Plan 2010-2019 that was aimed at detecting and devising care strategies that support children with learning difficulties and developing a teaching guide for a similar purpose. However, the report highlights that the country's Ministry of National Education, while considering the plan mentioned above, aims to train teachers in identifying and supporting children that have dropped explicitly out of school. Additionally, the Djibouti School Access and Improvement Programme, that has been funded by the International Development Association (IDA) and the World Bank More, is attempting to increase the capacity for in-service training for the administrative staff, principals, and teachers.

The UNESCO report highlights that the programme, which prioritizes girls and children with special needs, has aided in certifying a team of 20 qualified teachers that are responsible for teacher training and another 24 teachers and pedagogical advisers following the CBA to learning and teaching. The programme also considers inclusive education and has trained teachers that ensure children with learning disabilities receive school-based care. Hong (2012); Christoforidou and Kyriakides (2021); Mirza et al. (2023) believed that the entire concept of the CBA is the need for teachers to shift their focus to teaching students the significance of putting value to their learning process and reflecting on that so as to develop their learning skills and key competencies. In the words of the researcher:

“...what competency-based curriculum requires is reforming the way content knowledge is organised and brought to students, not denying its value”.

Mkonongwa (2018), and Simarmata and Mayuni (2023) argued otherwise, claiming that while schools and governments continue to advocate for a paradigm shift from content-based teaching to competency-based approaches to learning and teaching, content ought not to be taken for granted and that it should still be considered essential. However, both researchers shared a commonality: they both implied that competency-based learning and teaching ought to include attention to the styles and needs of the student; it should also provide the time that is needed for the student to acquire and repeatedly demonstrate or perform expected competencies. Additionally, the approach ought to create a supportive learning environment. Mkonongwa (2018) and Akongoh (2021) also claimed that CBA can be pursued via different teaching approaches. However, all curricula ought to be outcome-focused and evidence-based, and all strategies used in the teaching process ought to be matching with their learning domains.

Duc et al. (2017) emphasized that the renovation of teacher training, especially in new teaching and learning approaches, is a continuous trend across the globe and that the trend also requires the identification of a professional competency system where each teacher is required to achieve occupation and apprenticeship. However, this study focused on semi-developed nations and not developing nations such as Djibouti, therefore necessitating the need for the study to focus on Djibouti.

Teachers' Perceptions Towards the CBA Approach

Education is considered vital in any society as it aids in developing the ability to think creatively and critically and also develop interpersonal skills (Birgili, 2015; Calavia, Blanco & Casas, 2021). Basically, the universal consensus on this is an enabling mechanism process that aids in attaining knowledge, cultural transformations such as habits and beliefs, and also skills. Besides the mere fact that education is a tool that enhances the quality of life, it also appears to create a robust workforce, a healthy population, a safer community, creates awareness and fosters the right attitude (Edgerton et al., 2011; Reimers, 2020).

Sossion (2017) and Ondimu (2018), in the Kenyan context, discovered that the perceptions of most teachers were altered during the preparation process. For instance, the training sessions appeared to be ineffective due to the following factor: overloaded training content in the training sessions that were largely inadequate. Additionally, the researchers discovered that the facilitators/trainers were incompetent and lacked proper understanding or conceptualization of the CBC; as a result, they were unable to adequately facilitate the

training. Such issues changed the perceptions of the teachers towards the approach; most of them were demotivated and considered the approach difficult to implement. Sossion (2017) also stated that the headteachers were not trained on how to evaluate the learning and the teaching processes, and teachers, together with the core competencies and as a result, teachers perceived the approach as unnecessary and unprepared for.

Globally, there is a shift from viewing assessment as a singular component, such as the traditional end-of-end report card, to recognizing assessment as a fundamental aspect of daily instruction. This transition emphasizes its role in the ongoing enhancement of teaching and learning rather than a mere endpoint. Competency-Based Assessment (CBA) is thus characterized by assessments integrated into regular class activities, conducted by teachers who actively contribute to the design of assessment methods and decisions related to teaching and student learning, ultimately making judgments on student performance (Hill & McNamara, 2011); (Shermis & Vesta, 2011). Kha (2013) conducted a review of the Vietnamese educational assessment system, focusing on the theoretical significance, benefits, and characteristics of CBA. The study highlighted a lack of awareness among teachers regarding ongoing assessment. The research by Gonen and Akbarov (2015) discovered that instructors generally align with the principles of competency-Based Assessment (CBA), acknowledging the connection between students' learning assessment. However, participants noted challenges in implementing their beliefs due to institutional central assessment systems, demanding syllabuses within tight time limitation, and diverse educational backgrounds of students from the general education system. The study Ebisa Bekele et al. (2021) found that instructors held a negative of assessment for learning (CBA) practices. They perceived the Competency-Based Assessment for learning (CBAFL) as predominantly theoretical, emphasizing the need for more practical training for students to meet job standards. Participants identified factors affecting assessment practices, including the influence of traditional teaching and assessment methods, instructors prioritizing grading over fostering competency through practical assessment tools.

In an era where knowledge is being vastly created, teachers need to be adequately prepared to adopt a responsive and complex evolutionary approach (Gatlin, 2009; Hughes et al., 2020). The teaching profession ought to be developed in a procedural manner and especially the continuous improvement of training requirements to increase the chances of a successful implementation of ant curricular approach.

Teacher competencies in pedagogy greatly influence the effective implementation of any curriculum. Jackson & Nabwire (2017) together with Tadesse et al. (2021) investigated teacher competencies in pedagogical knowledge in teaching and discovered that majority of these teachers failed to apply a learner-centred approach. In conclusion, the researchers discovered that a large number of teachers were not competent in pedagogical knowledge for the implementation of any curriculum. This meant that if a teacher does not receive adequate training, they are less likely to be able to implement the CBA. On the same, Okoth (2016) assessed the training programs of teachers that implemented the revised English language curriculum and discovered that often, upon the implementation of a new curriculum, teachers will always use the previous curriculum's lesson plans.

The Role of Institutional preparedness in the implementation of the CBA approach

Teachers play a crucial role in creating learning opportunities and nurturing student potential (Zeiger, 2018; Kilag, Marquita & Laurente, 2023). Within the Competency-Based Approach (CBA) framework, teachers must shift from teaching to learning, engaging actively in informative assessment (Syomwene, 2017; Haris et al., 2021) and emphasizing expanded responsibilities. Syomwene (2017) highlights the need for teachers to foster connections between the curriculum and learners during instruction. This necessitates proficiency in effective educational approaches, comprehensive planning, crafting suitable assessment tools, and selecting instructional materials tailored to diverse student levels. Jeng'ere (2017) highlights the critical importance of thoughtful lesson plans for successful CBA execution. Farrel (2012) and Romiszowski (2024) define a lesson plans as detailed description encompassing procedures, content, materials, time, and the learning environment. Research, exemplified by Handwe and Mpofu (2017) explores the importance of training teachers in lesson planning and its impact on curriculum implementation, as seen in a study

assessing readiness among primary school teachers for a newly introduced third-grade curriculum in Zimbabwe.

This study aimed to evaluate teachers' proficiency in crafting lesson plans aligned with the new curriculum. Inadequate training negatively impacts teachers' competence in passing learners, as illustrated by Koma and Mwindaji (2015), who investigates the adherence of Tanzania teachers to formative assessment in line with CBA requirements. Results revealed that 86% of the teachers lacked a proper understanding of CBA lesson plans. Student engagement, in classroom activities, was generally low and less than 50% of observed classroom sessions incorporated formative assessment. Through in-service training, teachers can gain the necessary knowledge and skills for continuing formative assessments using assessments rubric. Chepkemoi et al. (2022) assessed the readiness of primary schools in Wareng Sub-County, Uasin Gishu County, Kenya, to implement the competency-based curriculum amid the COVID-19 pandemic. Findings indicated insufficient teaching resources, prompting the study to recommend increased government support for the provision of necessary materials and infrastructure for effective curriculum implementation during the crisis.

The hypotheses developed are as follows;

H1: *The current level of teacher training in primary schools contributes to the effective implementation of the CBA approach in Djibouti.*

H2: *Perceptions of primary school teachers towards the CBA approach influence their willingness to implement it in Djibouti.*

H3: *Institutional preparedness influences the accommodation and implementation of the CBA approach in Djibouti.*

The study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the effect of the current level of teacher training in primary schools on the implementation of the CBA approach in Djibouti?
2. What role do perceptions of primary school teachers towards the CBA approach play in influencing their willingness to implement it in Djibouti?
3. What is the effect of institutional preparedness on the adoption and implementation of the CBA approach in Djibouti?

Materials and Methods

Participants

The study collected data from 300 participants, who were primary school teachers in Djibouti. The sampling procedure in this study will be simple random sampling, where every participant will have an equal opportunity to be included in the sample. A basic random sample refers to a segment of a statistical population where each member within the segment has an equal likelihood of being selected, and in this study, this was aimed at reducing or minimizing any subjective bias. The objective of a simple random sample is to provide an impartial representation of the larger group without any inherent bias. The fundamental purpose of statistical analysis is to outline the foundation of the population. This refers to the group about which one seeks additional insights, and in this case, the primary school teachers in Djibouti. It also aims to validate a hypothesis or intends to ascertain a statistical outcome. This initial step involves identifying the population and ensuring that this group adequately encompasses the variables being investigated. However, it can be challenging, particularly when faced with a lack of readily available population lists and when the population is diverse and geographically dispersed. To address this problem, the researcher carried out an online survey, which eliminates the geographical distance problem.

The questionnaire was administered online via Google Forms in Djibouti. Quantitative surveys excel in capturing data from a broad and varied sample, bolstering the applicability of research outcomes. Standardized formats ensure data consistency, mitigating bias and enabling uniform analysis (Bagdoniene & Zemblyte, 2005). The objective framework of quantitative questionnaires minimizes researcher bias, fostering impartial data collection. Respondent anonymity in quantitative questionnaires fosters open and

truthful responses. The quantitative data's nature facilitates unbiased comparisons across diverse groups, variables, or time frames, yielding valuable insights (Wright, 2005).

Instrument

The instrument in this study were developed by the researcher as informed by the literature review on the factors influencing CBA approach. The questionnaire used in this study was a 45-item questionnaire, covering the variables of interest in this study. The researcher ensured validity and reliability of the research instrument. Validity refers to the extent to which the gathered data effectively encompasses the area of study (Ghauri & Gronhaug, 2005). In essence validity is synonymous with ensuring that the measurements precisely capture the intended variables (Field, 2005), and in the current study, the researcher does this by ensuring that the scale used to measure various constructs in the questionnaire are consistent. Content validity, also referred to as logical validity, addresses the extent to which a measurement faithfully represents all facets of a particular construct. The evaluation of content validity brings in a subjective element, requiring alignment on the comprehensive depiction of traits like sociability in a specific context (Pennington & Donald, 2003). Construct validity is defined as the extent to which a test accurately assesses the qualities it asserts or claims to measure (Brown, 1996), and to ensure construct validity, the researcher ensured that the selection of the items on the questionnaire is based on research. Criterion validity assesses the extent to which a measurement aligns with a particular outcome, commonly categorized into concurrent and predictive validity. In the case of concurrent validity, the measure is scrutinized against an outcome evaluated simultaneously.

Reliability is characterized as the degree to which a questionnaire, test, observation, or measurement procedure yields consistent results upon repeated trials. It encompasses three dimensions: equivalence (alternate-form reliability), stability (test-retest reliability), and internal consistency (homogeneity). In terms of equivalence, the first-dimension gauges the agreement between two or more instruments administered at nearly the same point in time. Equivalence is evaluated through a parallel forms approach, where alternative versions of the same measure are administered either to the same or different groups of respondents simultaneously or with a time gap (Litwin & Fink, 1995). Stability, the second aspect of reliability, is achieved when identical or similar scores are obtained through repeated testing with the same group of respondents, and this was achieved in this study by using standard scales of measurement such as Likert scale, and using questions that are simple and direct. Essentially, it ensures that scores remain consistent across different testing sessions. The third and final dimension of reliability is internal consistency, also known as homogeneity. This dimension focuses on the extent to which items on the test or instrument are measuring the same underlying construct. For instance, when developing a test to measure organizational commitment, assessing the reliability of each item is crucial. High correlations among individual items instil confidence in the overall reliability of the entire scale.

Statistically, the current study performed a Pearson's correlation between the score of each item of the questionnaire and the total score to determine validity. To test for reliability statistically, the study will utilize Cronbach's alpha, where a value of 0.7 would be the threshold to indicate sufficient internal consistency. This was performed in SPSS.

Data analysis

Data analysis is carried out using SPSS 25. Since the data collected in this study is quantitative, data analysis techniques used will also be quantitative. Both descriptive and inferential statistics are used to present and report the findings in this study. Regression analysis is used to investigate the relationship between dependent and independent variables in this study. The regression model is presented as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \dots + \beta_nX_n + \text{error}$$

With variables plugged in, the regression equation is as follows:

$$\text{Implementation of the CBA} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Level of Teacher Training}) + \beta_2 (\text{Teachers' Perceptions}) + \beta_3(\text{Institutional Preparedness}) + \text{error}$$

Key Problems and Solutions During the study

The main challenges faced in this study included the general lack of key literature on Djibouti and the implementation of CBA in the country. There was a number of challenges in terms of obtaining important statistics on the situation of CBA implementation in Djibouti. To address this challenge, the researcher relied on government publications and statistics from databases such as World Bank and Tradeconomics.com. To address the problems with enough peer reviewed literature, the researcher also included a few quasi-empirical literatures, which complemented the empirical literature cited in the study.

Ethics

The research observed all ethical considerations by ensuring that participants provided consent before participating. The research also sought approval from the Jiangsu University Approval Board before carrying out the study. The researchers declare no conflict of interest.

Results

Reliability analysis

Reliability analysis in SPSS is determined using Cronbach alpha, which measures the internal consistency of the Likert scale used in the research instrument. According to Tavakol and Dennick (2011), Cronbach's alpha that is <0.5 is *Poor*, >0.6 – *Questionable*, ≥ 0.7 – *Acceptable*, ≥ 0.8 – *Good*, and ≥ 0.9 – *Excellent*. In this study, therefore, a Cronbach's score of 0.7 and above will be acceptable, and an indication that the scale used in the research instrument is reliable. In Table 1 below, Cronbach alpha = 0.708, meaning that we conclude that the scale in the research instrument is reliable.

Table 1: Reliability test

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.708	24

Testing the Assumptions of Regression

The three main assumptions that are tested in this study are normality, homoscedasticity, and multicollinearity. For regression analysis to be performed, data has to be normally distributed, homoscedastic, and there should be no multicollinearity among the predictors or independent variables.

Testing Hypotheses

H1: *The current level of teacher training in primary schools contributes to the effective implementation of the CBA approach in Djibouti.*

To test this hypothesis, this study assessed the current level of training of primary school teachers and its effect on the implementation of a new competence-based approach (CBA) in primary school institutions. The decision rule for the hypotheses was as follows:

The hypothesis is supported if at least 50% of the predictors show statistical significance (p value <0.05). If less than 50% of the predictors show statistical significance, then the hypothesis is only partially supported, and when none of the predictors show statistical significance, then the hypothesis is not supported. Analysis is carried out at 95% confidence interval (critical value is 0.05). All hypotheses in this study are stated as alternative hypotheses. Table 2 shows that R Square = 0.546, which is an indication that

the predictors or the independent variables in the model explain 54.6% of dependent variable. In other words, teacher training explains 54.6% of the effective implementation of the CBA approach.

Table 2

Model	R	R Square	df	F	Sig
1	.739 ^a	.546	16, 299	21.313	0.0000

Table 2 also shows $F(16, 299) = 21.313$, and the p value <0.05 , which is an indication that the model can significantly predict the outcome, or the dependent variable. As shown in table 3, there are 16 predictors, and 9 out of these showed statistical significance (p values <0.05), which means, based on the decision rule stated earlier, that the hypothesis H1 is supported since 56.25% of the predictors showed statistical significance.

Table 3

Questionnaire Item		B	Sig
1	(Constant)	1.918	.000
	Training on the new Competency-Based approach guideline was done satisfactorily.	.078	.019
	I still need more training on how to use the new Competency-Based Approach.	.047	.007
	I have been adequately trained on lesson planning.	.042	.040
	I have been adequately trained on classroom management.	-.027	.142
	I have been trained on how to prepare relevant learning.	.034	.069
	I have been trained to guide learners with special education needs.	.029	.382
	I have been adequately trained to administer formative.	.019	.371
	I have been trained on how to assess learners different.	-.038	.023
	I have been equipped on how to teach digital literacy to learners.	.101	.002
	I have adequate training on how to use all the teaching aids.	-.014	.474
	I can now comfortably apply the new teaching method in teaching.	.004	.039
	I have been trained satisfactorily to teach communication and collaboration.	.115	.001
	I have been trained satisfactorily to teach critical thinking to learners.	-.014	.463
	I still feel unprepared to teach according to the new approach guidelines.	.024	.016
	I have been trained satisfactorily to assess problem solving skills to my learners.	.001	.971
	I been trained to teach citizenship and self-efficacy to my learners.	.092	.000

H2: *Perceptions of primary school teachers towards the CBA approach influence their willingness to implement it in Djibouti.*

To test this hypothesis, this study evaluated the perceptions of primary school teachers towards the newly introduced competency-based approach of learning and how they affect the implementation of the new competency-based approach. Table 4 shows that R Square = 0.645, which is an indication that the predictors or the independent variables in the model explain 64.5% of dependent variable. In other words, perceptions of primary school teachers towards the CBA approach explain 64.5% of the effective implementation of the CBA approach.

Table 4

Model	R	R Square	df	F	Sig
1	.803 ^a	.645	13, 299	39.935	0.0000

Table 4 also shows $F(13, 299) = 39.935$, and the p value <0.05 , which is an indication that the model can significantly predict the outcome, or the dependent variable. As shown in table 5, there are 12 predictors, and 9 out of these showed statistical significance (p values <0.05), which means, based on the decision rule stated earlier, that the hypothesis H2 is supported since 75% of the predictors showed statistical significance.

Table 5

Questionnaire Item	B	Sig
1 (Constant)	-.474	.100
The new approach has too much work load.	.065	.000
The competency-based approach is too time-consuming.	.028	.108
With the new approach, it is difficult to teach problem solving skills.	-.064	.001
The new approach encourages learners' participation in the learning process.	.223	.000
The new approach will improve the creativity and imagination of learners.	.136	.001
The new approach will promote critical thinking and problem-solving ability among learners.	.012	.432
The new approach will promote citizenship and efficacy among learners.	.084	.000
The new approach will enhance communication and collaboration among learners.	.007	.611
The new approach does not promote holistic development of a learners.	.013	.641
The new approach will adequately address the pertinent and contemporary issues in society.	.053	.000
The new approach could lead to the teachers' professional growth.	.120	.000
The newly introduced teaching techniques are easy to apply.	.066	.000
The impact of the new approach will take too long to be identified.	.388	.000

H3: *Institutional preparedness influences the accommodation and implementation of the CBA approach in Djibouti.*

By testing this hypothesis, the analysis will be assessing the level of institutional preparedness to accommodate and implement the new competency-based approach.

Table 6 shows that R square = 0.495, which is an indication that the predictors or the independent variables in the model explain 49.5% of dependent variable. In other words, institutional preparedness explains 49.5% of the effective implementation of the CBA approach.

Table 6

Model	R	R Square	df	F	Sig
1	.703	.495	9, 299	31.563	0.0000

In Table 6, $F(9, 299) = 31.563$, and the p value < 0.05 , which is an indication that the model can significantly predict the outcome, or the dependent variable. As shown in table 7, there are 9 predictors, and 5 out of these showed statistical significance (p values < 0.05), which means, based on the decision rule stated earlier, that the hypothesis H3 is supported since 55.6% of the predictors showed statistical significance.

Table 7

Questionnaire Item	B	Sig
1 (Constant)	1.929	.000
Our school has all the teaching and learning resources recommended by the new approach.	.069	.003
Our school has a few teachings and learning resources recommended by the new approach.	.172	.000
Our school has no teaching and learning resources recommended by the new approach.	.066	.000
Our school is completely prepared to implement the new approach.	-.065	.361
The school is not utilizing available teaching and learning resources.	.039	.052
The school administration is supportive on the implementation of the new approach.	-.004	.808
Other school staff is supportive on the implementation of the new approach.	.060	.000
Our school has created an enabling environment for performance-based learning.	.029	.200
The school has good networks with the education office in the city.	.144	.000

Discussion

The aim of the study was to investigate the role of teachers' level of training, their perception of the CBA curriculum, and institutional preparedness in the successful implementation of CBA. To establish this, a survey was issued to primary school teachers in Djibouti and through quantitative approaches, it was established that the current level of teacher training in primary schools contribute to the effective implementation of the CBA approach in Djibouti. The findings correspond with those of Duc et al. (2017) who claimed that before implementing the CBA approach, teachers ought to receive training as it is during this process that they develop professional competency for learners. Similarly, the findings of this study coincide with those of the UNESCO report which highlighted a lack of initial and in-service training for not only the teachers but also the general school staff members in Djibouti. According to the UNESCO report, there is need for teachers to acquire training before the implementation of the approach as it will greatly contribute to the effective implementation.

It was also established that perceptions of primary school teachers towards the CBA approach influenced their willingness to implement it in Djibouti. According to the findings, negative perceptions such as difficulties in teaching problem, and positive perceptions such as the CBA being able to address pertinent and contemporary issues in society greatly influenced the implementation of the approach. The findings are similar to those of Sossion (2017) and Ondimu (2018) who, in the Kenyan context, discovered that due to the lack of understanding of the approach, most teachers perceived it as inadequate for meeting the needs of the students. The findings also showed that institutional preparedness influenced the accommodation and the implementation of the CBA approach in Djibouti. Factors such as supportive staff members, a good relationship with the education offices in the city and available resources greatly improved the implementation of the CBA. The findings coincided with those of Jeng'ere's (2017) who highlighted the need to equip teachers with resources such as knowledge on lesson planning to facilitate the successful implementation of the CBA.

Practical Implications

As a significant number of the teachers had also not been exposed to training, and were unable to comfortably apply the new teaching approach in their teaching, implementing targeted professional developments programs that specifically focus on the practices and principles of the CBA could reduce the number of teachers that have been exposed to CBA training. Familiarization with the CBA is guaranteed to improve the effectiveness of the approach. These programs could include continuous training sessions, seminars and even workshops.

The findings of this study led to the conclusion that most primary schools in Djibouti lack all teaching and learning resources that have been recommended by the new approach and therefore, ensuring that the schools have necessary resources including digital tools, teaching aids and textbooks will improve the effectiveness of the approach.

Implications for future research

Based on the findings of this study, future studies could acquire both qualitative and quantitative data to capture teachers' explicit attitudes and perceptions of the CBA implementation. Also, future researchers could incorporate case studies to serve the complementary purpose of acquiring knowledge from a country that has successfully implemented the CBA. More researchers could also use information acquired from this study to conduct more research on the topic, as there is minimal research in the country, contributing to the lack of knowledge on the approach. Lastly, future research could also attempt to investigate how CBA can be adapted into the cultural context of the country, that is, there ought to be focus on how the curriculum integrates and respects local values, languages and traditions.

Conclusions

Previous decades have seen the CBA enter primary schools in Djibouti, but not without generating new stakes or sparking debates between the supporters and opposers of the approach. As Djibouti embarks on educational reforms and especially CBA implementation, concerns appear on the readiness of primary school teachers and the institutions in general, which created the basis for this study. The main objective of the study was to determine the primary school teachers' preparedness for the implementation of the CBA approach in Djibouti. Using a quantitative method, the findings concluded that the current level of teacher training, the perceptions of the teachers, and institutional preparedness significantly influenced the implementation of the CBA approach in Djibouti.

The study concluded that most teachers had received training, especially on teaching the learners citizenship and self-efficacy. As a significant number of the teachers had also not been exposed to training, they were unable to comfortably apply the new teaching approach in their teaching. Additionally, the study also concluded that further training on administering formative assessment was required since the approach required formative evaluation of each unit through the administration of a rubric to evaluate capability indicators. The approach is greatly recognized for its ability to cultivate critical thinking in its learners; the study concluded that teachers also need more training on how to satisfactorily teach and stimulate critical thinking to learners, as a significant number reported not having received training on such. Preparation of relevant learning material was not considered a problem as most of the primary school teachers were able to prepare relevant learning material.

Learning is considered an intricate process that requires collaboration and communication; the study's findings showed that teachers were slightly satisfied with their training in communication and collaboration. Great levels of satisfaction were identified with the training received on classroom management and the use of teaching aids, as most of them claimed to have been trained on how to guide learners with special needs. Since digital literacy was identified as a key competency of the CBA, it was important to assess the ICT skills of the primary school teachers in Djibouti. Most teachers claimed to have been trained in ICT and could comfortably teach digital literacy to learners. Despite a large number of primary school teachers receiving training on the different fractions of the implementation of the CBA, they still confessed to feeling unprepared to plan lessons and teach according to the new approach guidelines.

Generally, the perceptions of the primary school teachers influenced the willingness to implement the CBA. However, despite most teachers preferring the new learning approach to the traditional one, they strongly perceived it to have too much workload, which would translate to taking too much time, especially in lesson planning. Problem-solving has also been categorized as a key competency that each learner should attain through the CBA, and teachers have shown recognition of that. However, a significant number have also declared it difficult to instill problem-solving and critical thinking skills with the new approach. This could, perhaps, serve as more evidence of the need for further training for these primary school teachers on the new approach. The approach also encourages participation for both the learner and the teacher in the learning process.

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No additional data are available.

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